

Open Education (OE) in European Institutions of Higher Education - Survey 20

INTRODUCTION

Welcome to the 2023 edition of **SPARC Europe's** Survey regarding **Open Education (OE) and Open Education Resources (OER)**.

We plan to use the survey to design services to provide Open Education support in the future.

Your organisation does not need to be very active in OE or in all the areas covered in this survey for your answer to be valuable to us.

Taking the survey

We are interested in hearing from those **responsible for advancing OE and OER** in institutions, or who are actively considering it. Please forward the survey onto them, or complete it with their input. We are happy to receive multiple responses from an institution where different departments are involved or play different roles.

The survey deadline is **Friday, 26 January 2024, 23.59 CET** (Note - this deadline is an extension on the original deadline of 22 December 2023, 23.59 CET).

You don't need to complete the survey in one sitting.

Only questions marked with an asterisk * are mandatory.

The survey takes approximately **15 minutes to complete**. A PDF is downloadable [here](#).

No personal details are required to complete the survey, although you may supply your name and contact details to be informed of the outcomes of this study.

For questions, please reach out to **survey@sparceurope.org**.

The survey is managed by SPARC Europe - see [here](#) for our ethics and data protection policy. Answers will be reported in aggregate, personal data will be removed before the dataset is deposited on Zenodo with a CC0 licence.

By clicking 'Next' you confirm that you understand and agree to complete the survey.

ABOUT YOU AND YOUR ORGANISATION

* 1. Which of the following best describes your organisation?

Please select one answer

- University / Comprehensive institution (e.g. covering all or most academic disciplines)
- University of Applied Sciences (college-type or professional education institution which does not award PhDs, or does so in only a few disciplines)
- Technical university / University of technology
- Distance learning university
- Specialised institution (e.g. medical science, music and arts school)
- Teaching college
- Other (please specify)

* 2. In what country is your organisation based?

* 3. What is the name of your organisation? *Open text*

Please note - we use this information to help identify any duplicate responses.

* 4. We would like to contact you with the results of this survey and to inform you of future Open Education activities and surveys. Do you consent to being contacted by SPARC Europe for these purposes?

Your answer to this question has no impact on your survey response.

- Yes
- No

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YOUR DETAILS

5. Please provide your contact details so we can share the results of this survey and to inform you of future Open Education activities and surveys.

Name

Email Address

ABOUT YOU AND YOUR ORGANISATION

6. How long have you been involved in OE? *Please select one answer*

- less than 1 year
- 1-2 years
- 3-5 years
- 6-10 years
- more than 10 years
- I am not involved in OE

7. What is your role within your organisation?

8. In which department is your role based?

Please select all that apply

- Library
- Education and Teaching services
- Technology and Information Services
- Faculty
- Policy Office
- Other (please specify)

9. Which departments, other than your own, are involved in OE in your institution? *Please select all that apply*

- Library
- Education and Teaching services
- Technology and Information Services
- Faculty
- Policy Office
- Other (please specify)

- None of the above

10. What role does your department take in advancing OE or OER in your organisation? *Please select one answer*

- A lead role
- A supporting role
- We are still deciding
- We do not have a role
- Other (please specify)

BUILDING CAPACITY

This section focuses on understanding roles and capacity at your organisation in relation to OE/OER.

* 11. What services do you provide that relate to Open Education?

Please choose as many that apply

- Advice on copyright and open licensing
- Collection management / dealing with education publishers and aggregators
- Course pack provision
- Creation of open textbooks
- Data curation & interoperability
- Discovery services
- Information literacy, including open education
- Knowledge exchange
- OER co-creation
- OER provision (evaluation, selection, etc) to complement courses
- Management & storage service (e.g. repositories)
- Metadata to index digital resources
- Participatory design
- Training / Education
- Other (please specify)

- None of the above

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BUILDING CAPACITY

12. Please provide as much detail as you can about these services and which departments are involved in providing them. *Open text*

13. To what extent does your department have the skills it needs to support OE in these areas?

Please select one option per row

	Full set of skills	Many skills	Limited skills	No skills	Don't know
Advice on copyright and open licensing	<input type="radio"/>				
Collection management / dealing with education publishers and aggregators	<input type="radio"/>				
Course pack provision	<input type="radio"/>				
Creation of open textbooks	<input type="radio"/>				
Data curation & interoperability	<input type="radio"/>				
Discovery services	<input type="radio"/>				
Information literacy, including open education	<input type="radio"/>				
Knowledge exchange	<input type="radio"/>				
OER co-creation	<input type="radio"/>				
OER provision (evaluation, selection, etc) to complement courses	<input type="radio"/>				
Management & storage service (e.g. repositories)	<input type="radio"/>				
Metadata to index digital resources	<input type="radio"/>				
Participatory design	<input type="radio"/>				
Training / Education	<input type="radio"/>				
[Insert text from Other]	<input type="radio"/>				

14. For services for which you have 'Limited skills' or 'No skills' please explain whether there is just skills gap or you source the skills from elsewhere in your organisation or externally.

DEVELOPING SUPPORTIVE POLICY

We would like to understand your institutional policy context in this section. We refer to policy as a written document that stipulates the expectations related to OE for an institution. Its goal is to lead to the creation, increased use and/or support for improving OER. Beyond an institutional policy document, institutional strategic plans, laws, rules, green papers, white papers, roadmaps, declarations, and funding programmes are included in policy.

* 15. Does your organisation have a policy that addresses OE in any way? *Please select one answer*

- Yes
- Under development
- Under consideration
- No
- I don't know

If yes, please add link here:

DEVELOPING SUPPORTIVE POLICY

16. Is your organisation's OE policy part of a larger, overarching internal policy, or is it a standalone policy dedicated to OE? *Please select one answer*

- Standalone policy dedicated to Open Education
- Part of a larger, overarching Open Science policy
- Part of different larger, overarching policy
- Other (please specify)

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DEVELOPING SUPPORTIVE POLICY

* 17. Does your organisation have a formal task force, committee or other entity with an Open Education focus?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

DEVELOPING SUPPORTIVE POLICY

18. At what level in the organisation is the task force? *Please select all that apply*

- Institutional level
- Library level
- Departmental level
- Other (please specify)

19. Which departments are involved in the task force or committee? *Please select all that apply*

- Library
- Education and Teaching Support Services
- Technology and Information Services
- Faculty
- Policy Office
- Other (please specify)

20. Is the task force solely focused on Open Education or does it have a broader remit? *Please select one answer*

- Yes - it is solely focused on Open Education
- No - it has a focus on issues beyond Open Education
- No - it has a focus on a range of Open Science activities, including Open Education
- Other (please specify)

SUSTAINING OER

21. How many FTE (full time equivalent) staff members are dedicated to working on OE?

Note this excludes work on Open Access, Open Scholarship or Open Science.

If the answer cannot be precisely established, please provide a reasonable estimate.

Please select one answer

- 0
- Less than 1
- 1-5
- 6-9
- 10 or more
- Don't know

22. Does your organisation have a grant programme or seed funding that supports the creation of OERs?

This might be a programme dedicated to OE work or a broader scheme supporting educational innovation and / or excellence.

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

If yes, please provide the name of this programme or project and preferably a link to more information

23. From which budget or budgets does funding for OE come?

Please select all that apply

- Library budget
- Other institutional budget
- A national or regional project or programme
- A European project
- Other (please specify)

PROMOTING AND REINFORCING COOPERATION

24. Is your organisation involved in creating, maintaining or participating in OE networks or programmes? *Please select one option per row*

	Yes	No	Don't know
Networks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Projects / programmes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If yes, please list them

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ENCOURAGING ACCESS TO QUALITY OER

* 25. Do you actively seek to promote effective and inclusive access in OER programmes? *Please select one answer*

- Yes
- We are considering it
- No
- Other (please specify)

- Don't know

ENCOURAGING ACCESS TO QUALITY OER

26. How does your organisation promote effective and inclusive access in OE programmes? *Please select all that apply*

- Via a Working Group
- In collaboration with our diversity, equity and inclusion office
- As part of an institution-wide programme or strategy
- Other (please specify)

- Don't know

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REWARD & RECOGNITION

* 27. Are OE or OER rewarded or recognised in your organisation, whether formally or informally? *Please select one answer*

- Yes
- We are considering it
- No
- Other (please specify)

- Don't know

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REWARD & RECOGNITION

28. What recognition and reward mechanisms does your organisation use to promote OE & OER? *Open text*

* 29. We are keen to identify, encourage and showcase mechanisms that offer recognition and reward of OE and OER.

Are you willing for SPARC Europe to contact you regarding this?

Yes

No

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REWARD & RECOGNITION

30. Please provide your contact details so that we may contact you to discuss your mechanisms that offer recognition and reward of OE and OER.

Name

Email Address

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BENEFITS, CHALLENGES & AWARENESS RAISING

31. What are the major benefits you have identified from supporting Open Education in your organisation? *Please specify up to three*

Benefit 1

Benefit 2

Benefit 3

32. What are the major challenges that you have in supporting Open Education in your organisation? *Please specify up to three*

Challenge 1

Challenge 2

Challenge 3

33. We are particularly keen to understand the ways in which organisations raise awareness of the value of OE.

Please outline the ways in which you raise awareness of the value of OE, OER, Open Education Practices and Open textbooks in your organisation.

Open text

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ADDITIONAL COMMENTS

34. If you would like to add any further details to your survey response, please include these below. *Open text*

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END OF SURVEY

Thank you very much for taking this survey.